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Review Article

FORMULATION OF HERBAL TEA¹Vaishnavi K. Wankhede, ²Harishkumar K. Rathod, ³Dr. Swati Deshmukh^{1,2} Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, kondala zamare, Washim -444505³Assistant Professor Department Of pharmaceutics, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zamare, Washim -44450**Abstract:**

It has been demonstrated that herbal tea has several benefits. Tisanes are another name for herbal tea. A common and important element of social and cultural gatherings is tea. It is a preparation that strengthens immunity, maintains vitality, and regenerates cells. It eases worry, weariness, tension, and exhaustion. The beverage referred to as "herbal tea" is prepared with medicinal plants, herbs, and spices. Because of its medicinal and healing qualities, it is drunk all over the world without the need for caffeine. It can be purchased loose or in tea bag form. Herbal tea can be made by decoction or infusion with a total amount of water, or it can be diluted to an appropriate consistency and steeped for a predetermined amount of time. Natural bioactive substances like carotenoids, phenolic acids, flavonoids, coumarins, alkaloids, polyacetylenes, saponins, and terpenoids can be found in abundance in herbal teas and beverages. Herbal teas are concoctions prepared from the roots, leaves, fruits, and flowers of vibrant factory corridor plants. Herbal tea has antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory qualities, among other medicinal properties. Popular herbal teas include peppermint, ginger, ginseng, black, green, chamomile, and cinnamon teas. Most herbal teas can have one primary herbal component, or a combination of herbs used to achieve a certain goal. With herbal teas, connoisseurs can sample a wide range of flavors and possible health benefits. This study investigates the preparation and assessment of herbal teas, looking at the harmonious combining of therapeutic herbs to produce tasty and useful drinks.

Keyword: Tisanes, Camellia sinensis, Fermented, Phytochemicals, Antioxidant

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INTRODUCTION:

Herbal tea, also called tisane. It has increased in popularity due to its biological properties and certainly can be a complement to modern medicine. Dried leaves, seeds, grasses, flowers, nuts, or any other botanical components originating from plant species other than the commonly consumed tea species, *Camellia sinensis*, are consumed in this beverage. 1 Herbal tea is made using a combination of herbs in addition to those brewed in hot water. 2 Herbal remedies have been created by ancient cultures, such as Ayurveda and Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), to cure a variety of illnesses. 3 The herbs were mixed based on the similarities of health benefits for individual species. The current market has shown that most herbal-based products have shifted from using a single herb to polyherbs, which are believed to exert more pharmacological effects compared to a single herb. 4 Many studies have proved that herbs have the potential to prevent anemia. Sourashtra Herbal Tea (SHT) is composed of several herbs, each which helps in preventing anaemia and also helps to cure premenstrual problems in adolescent girls. 5 Medicinal plants have been used to treat and prevent different types of infectious diseases since prehistoric times. Nearly 60 to 90% of the total population worldwide uses plant-based medication. Medicinal plants could be used as tea or infusion to prevent or treat urinary tract infections. 6 Tea is the most commonly consumed beverage after water. It has a cooling, slightly bitter, and astringent flavor that many people enjoy. Tea is one of the most popular beverages, consumed daily in all domestic, social, and official meetings. It is a preparation that boosts immunity, keeps one active, rejuvenates cells, relieves stress, fatigue, tiredness, anxiety, and many more. British introduced teas into India in an attempt to break the Chinese monopoly on tea. In addition to serving as a beverage, many herbal teas are also consumed for their apparent medicinal benefits. Herbal tea is a non-caffeinated beverage made from the infusion or decoction of herbs, spices, or other plant material. Hence, in some countries like Europe, Tisanes or herbal teas are also known as infusions. Depending on the plant used and the method of preparation of the beverage, there are many varieties of herbal tea. Many more herbal tea varieties can be found than tea varieties for one simple reason: tea is extracted from one plant, while tisane is made from many

1.MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Sample Collection The required ingredients were collected and the leaves of *Ficus religiosa* were authenticated from Kendriya Sadan, Koti.

1.Ficus religiosa:

Biological Source- The leaves belonging to *Ficus religiosa* or Peepal tree is a species of fig that belongs to the Moraceae family. Chemical constituents- Phenols such as Gallic acid, rutin and gallic acid are present. It also contains Terpenoids such as Friedlein, luteol, Beta amyrin. Additionally, the presence of Rhein, anthraquinone and Taraxasterol are also observed.

Medicinal Uses- It is an antioxidant and antidiabetic. It also shows anticancer and anti-inflammatory effects.

Fig No.1- Ficus religiosa

2. Tulasi:

Biological Source- The leaves of *Ocimum tenuiflorum* or Holy Basil are considered sacred in many cultures and belong to the family Lamiaceae. Chemical constituents- It contains approximately 70% eugenol, carvacol (3%), eugenol-methyl-ether (20%) and caryophyllin

Fig No.2- Tulasi

Medicinal Uses- It acts as an immunomodulant. It also shows antidiabetic, analgesic effects and reduces cold, cough and other respiratory disorders.

3 Clove:

Biological Source- Cloves are the aromatic flower buds of a tree (Myrtaceae) *Syzygium aromaticum* (*Eugenia Caryophyllus*). **Chemical Constituents-** Its main constituent is eugenol which is an essential oil comprising total 23 identified Constituents, among them eugenol (76.8%), followed by Beta caryophyllene (17.4%), alpha humulene (2.1%) And eugenyl acetate (1.2%) as the main components.

Fig No.3- Clove

Medicinal Uses- It is used as an analgesic and antiviral due to presence of Eugenol. Cloves are good Expectorant that clears respiratory passage. The aromatic clove oil, when inhaled soothes the respiratory Conditions like asthma, cold, cough.

4. Cinnamon:

Biological Source- Cinnamon are dried inner bark of shoots of trees of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* belongs to Family Lauraceae. **Chemical Constituents-** Cinnamon oil contains cinnamaldehyde, eugenol, benzaldehyde, cumin aldehyde And other terpenes like pinene, cymene and caryophyllene.

Medicinal Uses- Cinnamon is fragrant and delicious spices with high antioxidant content. It also provides Antibacterial activity. Cinnamon may help fight throat pain and infection due to cold and cough

Fig No.4- Cinnamon**5 Ginger:**

Biological Source- It consists of rhizomes of *Zingiber officinale* belonging to family Zingiberaceae. **Chemical Constituents-** The pungent taste of ginger is due to presence of zingerol. It consists of 0.25-3% Volatile oils, 5-8% resinous matter, 56% starch and proteins.

Medicinal Uses- Ginger has antimicrobial property that can fight bacterial and viral infections. It has anti-Inflammatory property that can manage and reduce the risk of sore throat

Fig No.5- Ginger**Preparation of Herbal Tea Powder:**

The materials were shade dried and reduced to coarse powder. The powder was passed through appropriate Sieve and was weighed accurately. The F1, F2 and F3 were formulated as per the table

Formulation 1:

Ingredient	Quantity
Ficus religiosa	5g
Ginger	0.01g
Tulasi	0.1g

Formulation 2:

Ingredient	Quantity
Ficus religiosa	5g
Clove	2g
Cinnamon	2g

Formulation 3:

Ingredients	Quantity
Ficus religiosa	5g
Cinnamon	2g
Tulasi	1g

2. TYPE OF HERBAL TEAS

1. Floral Herbal Teas

These teas are made from flowers and are often soothing and aromatic.

- **Chamomile:** Calming and great for sleep and digestion
- **Lavender:** Known for its relaxing properties and pleasant fragrance.
- **Hibiscus:** Tart and tangy, with high vitamin C content
- **Rose:** Floral, soothing, and often used for skin health.
- **Jasmine:** Known for its sweet fragrance and mild, soothing taste.
- **Linden Blossom:** Used for relaxation and sleep, often sweet-tasting.
- **Elderflower:** Often used to relieve cold and flu symptoms.
- **Orange Blossom:** Sweet and fragrant, good for stress relief

2. Leaf-Based Herbal Teas

- **Peppermint:** Known for digestive aid and a refreshing, cooling taste.
- **Spearmint:** Similar to peppermint, but milder in flavor.
- **Lemon Balm:** Relaxing, often used for anxiety and sleep disorders.
- **Catnip:** Calming for both humans and pets, with a mild flavor.
- **Lemon Verbena:** Refreshing, with citrus notes, and good for digestion.
- **Rosemary:** Energizing, often used for mental clarity and focus.
- **Thyme:** Antibacterial and soothing for the respiratory system.

3. Root-Based Herbal Teas

- **Ginger:** Known for its digestive and anti-inflammatory properties.
- **Licorice Root:** Sweet and soothing, often used to support respiratory health.
- **Turmeric:** Anti-inflammatory, often paired with ginger and black pepper.
- **Valerian Root:** Used as a natural sedative for relaxation and sleep.
- **Ashwagandha:** Known for its adaptogenic

properties, helping to reduce stress and anxiety.

- **Dandelion Root:** Often used for liver detox and digestive health.
- **Dong Quai:** A traditional Chinese herb, often used for women's health

Health Benefit Of Herbal Teas

1. Chamomile Tea

• Benefits:

Chamomile is well-known for its calming and relaxing properties, making it a popular choice for improving sleep and reducing anxiety.

• Health Benefits:

- Promotes relaxation and helps with sleep
- Reduces symptoms of anxiety and stress
- Supports digestive health by easing indigestion and bloating
- Anti-inflammatory properties may help with skin irritations

2. Peppermint Tea

• Benefits:

Peppermint tea is refreshing and soothing, and it can help with a variety of digestive issues.

• Health Benefits:

- Eases indigestion, bloating, and gas
- Relieves headaches and migraines
- Soothes muscle aches or tension o
May improve concentration and mental clarity

3. Ginger Tea

• **Benefits:** Ginger tea is known for its strong, spicy flavor and its ability to support the digestive system

• Health Benefits:

- Relieves nausea, especially in cases of motion sickness or morning sickness during pregnancy
- Reduces inflammation and muscle pain
- Improves digestion and relieves bloating
- Supports immune health by promoting circulation and combating infections

CONCLUSION:

Herbal teas have been consumed for centuries and continue to be popular beverages worldwide. These natural infusions offer a range of flavors and aromas, and they are also known for their potential health benefits. Throughout this review, we explored the scientific literature on four commonly consumed herbal teas: lavender tea, ginger tea, turmeric tea and cinnamon tea. Lavender tea, derived from the aromatic lavender plant, has been associated with

calming effects and potential benefits for sleep and relaxation. The research suggests that lavender tea may help reduce anxiety, improve mood and promote better sleep quality. However, more studies are needed to further elucidate its mechanisms of action and therapeutic potential. Ginger tea, made from the roots of the ginger plant, has a long history of use in traditional medicine. The bioactive compounds present in ginger, such as gingerols and shogaols, exhibit antiinflammatory, antioxidant, and digestive properties. Ginger tea has been studied for its potential to alleviate nausea, reduce inflammation, and support digestive health. Emerging research also indicates its potential in managing pain and improving cardiovascular health. Turmeric tea, derived from the bright yellow rhizome of the turmeric plant, contains curcumin, a powerful compound with various health benefits.

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